

Work Package 7, Milestone 7.9: Existing services updated to existing data types

Summary

A review of takeup of metadata standards discovered that the greatest gap in West-Life services was in use of .pdb files instead of the now preferred mmCIF format. This is particularly important for large structures, where the number of atoms, residues or chains may exceed the limits of the fixed-width PDB format. Such structures are increasingly common, largely due to advances in cryo Electron Microscopy.

Sustainability

Conversion to mmCIF was also identified as a sustainability issue. When the inevitable tipping point arrives, services that cannot import and export mmCIF will be perceived as less usable.

Outcome

West-Life partners have made significant progress towards use of mmCIF:

- DipCheck (<http://cluster.embl-hamburg.de/cgi-bin/dipcheck/dipcheck.cgi>) is a validation tool for the evaluation of protein backbone geometry. Users upload a file of protein coordinates, which can now be in mmCIF format as an alternative to the PDB format. (EMBL-Hamburg)
- The ARP/WARP web service (<https://arpwarp.embl-hamburg.de>) runs several modes for building proteins, nucleic acids and ligands. It accepts mmCIF for ligands but not proteins (EMBL-Hamburg)
- The PDB_REDO service (<https://pdb-redo.eu>) reads and writes mmCIF coordinate files. Version 8 of PDB-REDO will use mmCIF internally (NKI).
- The PDB-REDO databank contains optimised versions of existing PDB entries. Re-refined and rebuilt structures can be downloaded as mmCIF files (NKI).
- The new HADDOCK portal for protein-protein docking accepts mmCIF input (UU). More details are provided in D7.5.
- The DISVIS portal for visualising the information content of distance restraints accepts mmCIF input (<https://milou.science.uu.nl/cgi/services/DISVIS/disvis/>) (Utrecht)
- 3DBionotes (<https://3dbionotes.cnb.csic.es/ws>) provides various annotations of macromolecular structures. It will accept the base structure in either PDB or mmCIF format (CSIC).

Most CCP4 web services do not use coordinate files as input, but may output coordinate files after successful phasing. The underlying programs are being updated to use the Gemmi software library which will provide seamless i/o to mmCIF format. As this involves a major overhaul of the CCP4 software suite, it is progressing on a longer timescale. Progress on Gemmi can be followed at <https://gemmi.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

More details on the adoption of mmCIF are reported in West-Life Deliverable 7.9.

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